

THE INFLUENCE OF AUTHORITARY PARENTING STYLES IN THE FAMILY ON THE SPEAKING ABILITY OF EARLY CHILDREN IN PAUD IN CIREUNGHAS DISTRICT

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Abstraction

Language development, particularly vocabulary mastery and speaking skills, is an important aspect of early childhood growth and development. One factor influencing a child's language development is the parenting style applied within the family. This study aims to determine the speaking skills of early childhood and analyze the influence of authoritarian parenting styles in families on the development of vocabulary and speaking skills of early childhood in early childhood education (PAUD) in Cirebon District. This study used a quantitative approach with a survey method. The study population was 1,311 parents of early childhood children (4-6 years old) attending PAUD/TK in Cirebon District, with a sample of 78 respondents selected using a purposive sampling technique. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using prerequisite tests and simple linear regression analysis. The results showed that the data were normally distributed and the relationship between variables was linear. The results of the simple linear regression test indicated that authoritarian parenting styles significantly influenced the development of vocabulary and speaking skills of early childhood. This finding suggests that the higher the implementation of authoritarian parenting styles in the family, the greater the potential for inhibiting the development of vocabulary and speaking skills of children. Therefore, a more communicative and dialogical parenting pattern needs to be developed by parents to optimally support the language development of early childhood.

Keywords: *Authoritarian Parenting Style, Speaking Ability, Early Childhood.*

INTRODUCTION

Early childhood is a crucial developmental phase that determines subsequent stages. Between the ages of 0–6, brain development is so rapid that this period is often referred to as the golden age (Anggita, 2020). One aspect of development that experiences significant growth during this phase is language development, which includes vocabulary mastery and speaking skills as children's primary means of communicating, interacting, and understanding their surroundings (Da & Pires, 2018). Early childhood language development is heavily influenced by stimulation from the immediate environment, particularly the family. Language develops not only through biological processes but also through intense and ongoing social interactions. Children who receive adequate language stimulation tend to have better vocabulary and speaking skills than those who receive minimal verbal stimulation (Hidayah et al., 2021). Therefore, the quality of interactions between parents and children is a crucial factor in supporting early childhood language development.

Every family has a different parenting style for raising children, which is generally influenced by the parenting style the parents received previously. Parenting can be defined as a pattern of interaction between parents and children that encompasses meeting physical and emotional needs, as well as the process of socializing values and norms that apply in society (Ayun, 2017). In the context of language development, parenting also reflects how parents communicate with their children, provide language examples, and create a climate of communication within the family. One of the parenting styles commonly encountered in society is authoritarian parenting. This parenting style is characterized by strict rules, one-way communication, and high demands for obedience from children to parents. In authoritarian parenting, children tend to have limited ability to express opinions, ask questions, or express ideas freely. This condition has the potential to hinder children's vocabulary development and speaking skills due to the limited opportunities for children to practice active communication. Previous research has shown that parenting styles that lack adequate emotional support and communication stimulation can negatively impact children's language development (Brantasari, 2022). Children raised in family environments with rigid and limited

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communication tend to have less than optimal language development. This suggests a potential causal relationship between parenting styles and early childhood language development. Field observations indicate that in Cirebon District, there is variation in the speaking abilities of early childhood children in various early childhood education institutions. Several teachers reported that some children have limited vocabulary, are less fluent in speaking, and lack confidence in communication. This condition is thought to be influenced not only by the learning process at school but also by parenting styles implemented in the family environment. Children raised with authoritarian parenting styles tend to have fewer opportunities for dialogue, which can hinder their vocabulary development and speaking skills. Based on this description, research into the influence of authoritarian parenting styles in families on vocabulary development and speaking skills in early childhood is important, particularly in early childhood education centers (PAUD) throughout Cirebon District. This research is expected to provide an empirical overview of the relationship between authoritarian parenting styles and early childhood language development.

IDENTIFICATION OF PROBLEMS

Based on the research background, the problems that can be identified are as follows:

1. There are still parents in Cirebon District who apply an authoritarian parenting style, which is characterized by strict rules, one-way communication, and minimal opportunities for children to express their opinions.
2. The vocabulary development of early childhood in several PAUD institutions in Cirebon District still varies, where some children have limited vocabulary and are less active in responding to verbal communication.
3. Some early childhood children show speaking abilities that have not developed optimally, such as less fluent speech and a lack of confidence in conveying ideas.
4. Lack of parental understanding regarding the impact of authoritarian parenting styles on the language development of early childhood.
5. There is no empirical data available that specifically examines the influence of authoritarian parenting patterns in families on the development of vocabulary and speaking skills of early childhood children in Cirebon District.

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

In accordance with the problem formulation in the background, the research questions are formulated as follows:

1. How are the speaking skills of early childhood children in PAUD throughout Cirebon District?
2. Is there an influence of authoritarian parenting patterns in families on the development of vocabulary and speaking skills of early childhood children in PAUD in Cirebon District?

LITERATURE REVIEW AND MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Authoritarian Parenting Style

Parenting styles are the overall patterns of interaction between parents and children in the process of raising, educating, and shaping children's behavior. Parenting styles encompass how parents set rules, set boundaries, show affection, and communicate with their children (Anisah, 2011; Ayun, 2017). Parenting styles are relatively consistent over time and significantly influence children's development. One widely recognized parenting style is authoritarian parenting. According to Santrock (2011), authoritarian parenting is a restrictive and punitive style, in which parents demand absolute obedience from their children without allowing for discussion. This parenting style is characterized by a high level of control and a low level of emotional warmth (Istiqomah Hidayati RAKT, 2014). Baumrind explains that the main characteristics of authoritarian parenting include one-way communication, strict punishment, demands for uncompromising obedience, and minimal opportunities for children to express their opinions. Children are expected to obey parental authority, while emotional needs and freedom of expression receive little attention (Nur Fadhilah et al., 2019). Authoritarian parenting tends to create a rigid and oppressive family climate, which can impact a child's psychological well-being, such as fear, low self-confidence, and limited ability to express opinions. These conditions can potentially impact a child's language development, particularly speaking skills and vocabulary mastery.

Speaking Skills and Vocabulary Development in Early Childhood

Language development is a crucial aspect of early childhood development. Language serves as a means of communication, a tool for thinking, and a medium for expressing ideas and emotions. Children's language development encompasses several key components, including phonology, vocabulary, syntax, semantics, and

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pragmatics (Jamaris in Jurnal et al., 2020). Speaking skills are part of expressive language, namely a child's ability to verbally convey thoughts, feelings, and desires so that others can understand them (Iskandar et al., 2021). At an early age, speaking skills develop along with a child's expanding vocabulary and the intensity of verbal interactions with their surroundings. Vocabulary is the primary foundation for developing speaking skills. The more vocabulary a child masters, the better they will be able to construct sentences and convey ideas coherently. Vocabulary development is greatly influenced by a child's language experiences, both through direct interactions with parents and other social environments (Nurmila & Ntelu, 2023). Various theories explain the process of children's language development, including nativism, which emphasizes innate factors; behaviorism, which emphasizes the role of the environment and habituation; and interactionism, which views language development as the result of the interaction between a child's internal abilities and environmental stimulation (Putri, 2021a). In this context, the family environment plays a dominant role in providing quality language stimulation.

The Relationship Between Authoritarian Parenting Styles and Children's Speaking Ability

The relationship between parenting styles and the development of early childhood speech is close and mutually influential. Children learn language through imitation, interaction, and response to communication within their immediate environment, particularly their family. Therefore, the communication patterns established by parents through specific parenting styles will significantly influence the quality of a child's language development (Wiyono et al., 2024). Authoritarian parenting styles characterized by one-way communication and high demands for compliance tend to limit children's opportunities to actively speak. Children are given little space to ask questions, express opinions, or express feelings, limiting the frequency and quality of speaking practice. This situation has the potential to hinder vocabulary development and speaking skills in early childhood (Brantasari, 2022). Furthermore, a rigid and stressful parenting environment can create fear and anxiety in children. Children become less confident in communicating due to concerns about being reprimanded or punished when speaking. As a result, children tend to be verbally passive, less responsive, and have difficulty expressing ideas verbally (Sherly Nurul Padilah et al., 2025). Authoritarian parenting not only impacts the emotional aspects of children, but also has direct implications for the development of expressive language, especially speaking skills and vocabulary mastery in early childhood.

Research Hypothesis

Based on the theoretical study and relevant previous research results, the hypothesis in this study is formulated as follows:

1. H_0 : There is no influence of authoritarian parenting patterns in the family on the development of vocabulary and speaking skills of early childhood children in PAUD throughout Cirebon District.
2. H_1 : There is an influence of authoritarian parenting patterns in the family on the development of vocabulary and speaking skills of early childhood children in PAUD throughout Cirebon District.
- 3.

Research Thinking Framework

Based on several references from the literature review, the following is the research framework below..

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Figure 1. Framework of Thought

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Types and Sources of Research Data

Data Types

This study used a quantitative approach to empirically test the influence of authoritarian parenting styles on early childhood vocabulary development and speaking skills. The quantitative approach was chosen because it allows researchers to objectively measure the relationships between variables through numerical data and statistical analysis. The type of data used in this study is quantitative data, namely data obtained from the results of measuring research variables using research instruments in the form of questionnaires or questionnaires compiled based on indicators of authoritarian parenting patterns and the development of vocabulary and speaking skills in early childhood.

Data source

Primary Data

Primary data was obtained directly from research respondents through questionnaires. Respondents in this study were parents and/or other parties directly involved in the care of early childhood children enrolled in early childhood education institutions (PAUD) throughout Cirebon District. The questionnaire was used to measure the level of authoritarian parenting practices within families and the development of children's vocabulary and speaking skills.

Secondary Data

Secondary data was obtained from various supporting sources relevant to the research, including PAUD institution documents, student data, and scientific literature in the form of books, journal articles, and previous research related to parenting patterns and early childhood language development. Secondary data was used to strengthen the theoretical foundation and support the analysis of the research findings.

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Population and Sample

Population

The population in this study was all residents in Cirebon District who have early childhood children (4-6 years old) who are attending PAUD/TK institutions, totaling 1,311. The community in question is the parents (father and/or mother) who live and are directly involved in the daily care of the children.

Sample

The research sample is a part of the population selected to represent the entire research population. The sample was determined using a purposive sampling technique, namely the researcher set limits for the sample, namely: (1) living in the same house as the child and being directly involved in daily care; (2) willing to voluntarily participate in the research by filling out the questionnaire completely and honestly; (3) able to read and write to understand the research instrument; and (4) not having communication disorders or special conditions that could hinder participation in the research.

Data Analysis Techniques

The collected data was analyzed using quantitative statistical analysis techniques. The data analysis was carried out in several stages, namely:

1. Descriptive Analysis, to describe the characteristics of respondents and the tendency of authoritarian parenting patterns and vocabulary development and speaking skills of early childhood.
2. Statistical Assumption Test, which includes normality tests and other prerequisite tests to ensure that the data is suitable for inferential analysis.
3. Inferential analysis was used to test research hypotheses regarding the influence of authoritarian parenting on vocabulary development and speaking skills in early childhood. The analytical techniques used were regression analysis or other statistical techniques relevant to the research objectives.

DATA ANALYSIS RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Description

This study was conducted to determine the effect of authoritarian parenting on children's speaking ability. Data were collected through questionnaires distributed to 78 children. The independent variable in this study was authoritarian parenting, while the dependent variable was children's speaking ability. Prior to the analysis, prerequisite tests were conducted, including validity, reliability, normality, and linearity. The results of these tests will be described in the following subchapter.

Prerequisite Test

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity testing aims to determine the extent to which the statement items in the instrument are able to measure the research variables. Validity criteria are determined by comparing the calculated r-value and the table r-value. An item is considered valid if the calculated r-value exceeds the table r-value.

Table 1. Validity Test

No	r count	r table	Information
1	0.068	0.3438	Invalid
2	0.109	0.3438	Valid
3	0.182	0.3438	Valid
4	0.310	0.3438	Valid
5	0.129	0.3438	Valid
6	0.359	0.3438	Valid
7	0.357	0.3438	Valid
8	0.465	0.3438	Valid
9	0.146	0.3438	Valid
10	0.453	0.3438	Valid
11	0.439	0.3438	Valid
12	0.249	0.3438	Valid

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13	0.404	0.3438	Valid
14	0.572	0.3438	Valid
15	0.480	0.3438	Valid
16	0.426	0.3438	Valid
17	0.292	0.3438	Valid
18	0.549	0.3438	Valid
19	0.583	0.3438	Valid
20	0.476	0.3438	Valid
21	0.542	0.3438	Valid
22	0.271	0.3438	Valid

Based on Table 1 above, it can be seen that of the 22 questions tested, 21 were declared valid and 1 was declared invalid. Invalid items were removed from the research instrument and not used in further data analysis.

Reliability test

Reliability testing was conducted to determine the consistency of the research instrument. An instrument is considered reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value is > 0.60.

Table 2. Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.684	0.748	23

Based on Table 4.2 above, the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.684, which is greater than 0.60. Therefore, it can be concluded that all questions in this research questionnaire are reliable and can be used for research data collection.

Data Normality Test Results

The normality test aims to determine whether research data is normally distributed. The test was conducted using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov/Shapiro–Wilk test. Data are considered normally distributed if the Sig. value is > 0.05.

Table 3. Data Normality Test

Criteria	Mark
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.200
Conclusion	Normally Distributed Data

Linearity Test

The linearity test is used to determine whether the relationship between the independent and dependent variables is linear. The relationship is considered linear if the Sig. Linearity value is <0.05.

Table 4. Linearity Test

Criteria	Mark	Conclusion
Deviation from Linearity Sig.	0.789	There is a Linear Relationship
F count	0.701	
F table (17;59)	1,773	

Based on the results of the linearity test, the deviation from linearity Sig. value was obtained at 0.789 which is greater than 0.05. In addition, the calculated F value is 0.701 and the F table (17;59) ≈ 1.773, so the calculated F < F table. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant linear relationship between the authoritarian parenting variable and children's speaking ability.

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Hypothesis Test Results

Simple Linear Regression Test (t-Test)

A simple linear regression test was conducted to determine the effect of authoritarian parenting on vocabulary development and speaking skills in early childhood. The test was conducted by examining the t-value and significance (Sig.). The hypothesis was accepted if Sig. < 0.05.

Table 5. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	4,174	1,309	-	3,188	0.002
Authoritarian Parenting Style	1,103	0.031	0.971	35,384	0,000

Based on table 4.5 above, it can be seen that the significance value (Sig.) is 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. In addition, the calculated t value of 35.384 is greater than the t table $(0.025; 76) \approx 1.992$. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between authoritarian parenting styles on children's speaking ability. In other words, the research hypothesis stating that 'there is an influence of authoritarian parenting styles on children's speaking ability' is accepted.

DISCUSSION

The research results show that authoritarian parenting styles in families influence the vocabulary development and speaking skills of early childhood education children in early childhood education centers (PAUD) throughout Cirebon District. This finding reinforces the view that the family environment, particularly the interaction and communication patterns established by parents, plays a crucial role in early childhood language development. Authoritarian parenting is characterized by high levels of control, rigid rules, and one-way communication from parent to child. This can potentially limit children's opportunities to actively participate in conversations, ask questions, and verbally express ideas and feelings. Consequently, children receive less than optimal language stimulation, impacting vocabulary mastery and speech fluency.

The results of this study align with Brantasari's (2022) findings, which state that parenting styles that lack emotional support and communication stimulation can hinder children's language development. Children raised in families with rigid communication tend to have low self-confidence in speaking and are less verbally active. Similar findings were also presented by Padilah et al. (2025), who found a significant relationship between parenting styles and the language development of preschool-aged children. Vygotsky's interactionist and sociocultural theories emphasize that children's language development is highly dependent on meaningful social interactions. When these interactions are limited and non-dialogic, as in authoritarian parenting, children's opportunities to develop expressive language skills are further limited. This explains why children in authoritarian parenting environments tend to exhibit less than optimal speech skills. The results of this study confirm that authoritarian parenting not only impacts children's emotional and social aspects but also has direct implications for vocabulary development and early childhood speech skills. These findings provide empirical evidence that the quality of parenting within the family is a crucial factor to consider in efforts to improve early childhood language development.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that has been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. The speaking ability and vocabulary mastery of early childhood children in PAUD throughout Cirebon District shows variation, where some children have not achieved optimal language development.
2. Authoritarian parenting patterns in families have been proven to have an influence on the development of vocabulary and speaking skills of early childhood children in PAUD throughout Cirebon District.
3. The higher the implementation of authoritarian parenting patterns in the family, the greater the potential for hampering the development of vocabulary and speaking skills in early childhood.

Suggestion

Based on the research results and conclusions obtained, the suggestions that can be put forward are as follows:

1. For Parents
Parents are expected to reduce their authoritarian parenting style and begin building more open, warm, and dialogical communication with their children. Providing children with opportunities to speak, ask questions, and express their opinions needs to be increased to support vocabulary development and speaking skills.
2. For Teachers and Early Childhood Education Institutions
Early childhood education teachers are expected to provide more intensive language stimulation in the school environment, especially for children from families with authoritarian parenting styles. Furthermore, schools can educate and mentor parents about the importance of parenting styles that support children's language development.
3. For Further Researchers
Further research is recommended to examine the influence of various types of parenting patterns more comprehensively or add other variables, such as the social environment and learning methods at school, in order to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that influence early childhood language development.

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